

The Extreme Skydiver: Universal Jump Parameter, Critical Path Points, and Flight Instabilities

Antonio Corvo
United States Air Force (Retired)
March 17, 2026

The problem of high-altitude skydivers experiencing large variations in atmospheric density is investigated. Past efforts have mostly concentrated on finding altitude and velocity solutions to match recorded data. The procedure here goes past altitude and velocity and includes calculating the higher derivatives of acceleration and its derivative, the jolt, and the jolt's derivative. It is shown the peaks in acceleration and jolt provide insight to the dynamics of the problem and explain instabilities seen in one case where no small stabilizing parachute was used, specifically, instabilities coincide with the skydiver reaching peak positive acceleration. The analysis was accomplished by dividing the jump profile into five regions based on air densities at approximately $10,000\text{ m}$ increments and using Taylor series expansions in each increment. A parameter in the derivations, referred to as a universal jump parameter, was useful in simplifying and organizing the analysis. Calculated quantities, important in documenting freefall records, such as peak velocity and total free-fall time, agree very well with recorded data.

I. INTRODUCTION

As aircraft achieved higher altitudes, and with the dawn of the space program, research began addressing whether a human can eject from high altitudes and survive. The test systems usually consisted of a pod attached to a high-altitude balloon rising to the desired altitude, where the participant stepped out to begin the journey back to earth. Extreme skydiving continues to attract daredevils seeking new altitude records along with public and scientific interest.

There have been three successful, well documented, extreme altitude jumps, with many more at medium altitudes.¹⁻¹² Table I summarizes the three highest jumps that will be analyzed here. Two of the individuals (Kittinger and Eustace) used small “drogue” parachutes for stabilization during their descents prior to their main parachute deployment. Two individuals (Baumgartner and Eustace) exceeded the speed of sound (Mach 1). Baumgartner experienced severe instabilities during his fall but did not deploy a drogue chute, distinguishing his jump from the others. The time, altitude, and potential causes of these instabilities are discussed in the analysis below.

The Kittinger and Eustance reference data are limited to important profile points such as initial height, peak speed, attitude at peak speed, and total free fall time. The Baumgartner jump data includes detailed speed, altitude, and time data. These can be found in Refs. 8 and 9. Reference 9 also approaches the data from an educational perspective and is a good starting point for educators interested in individual or group projects.

The extreme skydiver problem allows students to examine how a typical physics model increases in complexity as more conditions are applied. In this case, from free fall with zero drag, to free fall with constant drag, to free fall with variable drag, and whatever conditions students may wish to add, for example, gravity as a function of altitude. Of course, each successive model must reduce to the previous version under the appropriate limits or conditions.

II. BASIC FORMULATION

The basic equation for a skydiver's acceleration, dv/dt , for the case where air density varies with altitude, is written as a function of the acceleration due to gravity and a drag term in the form^{2,10}

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = -g + be^{-\lambda y}v^2. \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), v is the velocity, t is time, g is the acceleration due to gravity, b is related to the drag coefficient, y is the altitude, and λ is the atmospheric density rate constant. If we set $\lambda = 0$, the problem reverts to a low altitude jump where the air density and the drag are assumed roughly constant with solutions that involve hyperbolic functions.¹⁰ If $b = 0$, the problem further reduces to the simple freefall of an object in a vacuum. In Eq. (1), b can be expressed as g/v_t^2 , where v_t is the terminal velocity. A small/large terminal velocity relates to a large/small drag coefficient.

Table I. Historic High-Altitude Jumps

Event (Skydiver Name)	Initial Altitude (m)	Maximum Recorded Speed (m/s)	Notes
Joseph Kittinger 1960	31,300	274	-Used a drogue chute -References 1 and 2
Felix Baumgartner 2012	38,969	377	-No drogue chute -Experienced extreme instabilities -Exceeded Mach 1 -References 4-10
Alan Eustace 2015	41,453	367	-Used a drogue chute -Exceeded Mach 1 -References 11-12

The choice of the exponential term on the far right of Eq. (1), to model atmospheric density, was a tradeoff between simplicity and more rigorous models. It assumes a mean atmospheric temperature, captured through λ , and is derived from the Barometric formula and Ideal Gas Law.¹³ Its utility compensates for its rough accuracy over all altitude ranges of interest. In this study, Eq. (1) is divided over five regions defined by unique physical characteristics of the atmosphere, as well as physical dynamics of the skydiver's jump profile. Thus, to compensate for the simple air density model in Eq. (1), λ will be determined by a value that best captures these regions.

In finding a solution to Eq. (1), it is convenient to define a variable z given by

$$z = \frac{2g}{\lambda v_t^2} e^{-\lambda y}. \quad (2)$$

Defining y_0 as the initial jump altitude, we can further define the parameter z_0 from Eq. (2) as

$$z_0 = \frac{2g}{\lambda v_t^2} e^{-\lambda y_0}. \quad (3)$$

The importance of z_0 , is understood by noting every physical parameter defining the specific jump profile is contained in Eq. (3); the acceleration of gravity, drag expressed by the terminal velocity, and the atmospheric density rate. Furthermore, since z is a function of y , its derivative is related to velocity; a feature that will be used in later derivations. Thus, z_0 becomes a useful comprehensive,

or universal, jump parameter and initial condition (it will be assumed for this study that the initial velocity is always zero). In terms of z , Eq. (1) becomes

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = -g + \frac{\lambda}{2} z(y)v^2. \quad (4)$$

The solution to Eq. (4) cannot be expressed in terms of elementary functions. Thus, attempts such as in Refs. 2 and 10 included analytical approximations supplemented by numerical analysis; an approach followed below but from a different perspective and methodology.

III. REGIONAL EXTREMA AND TAYLOR SERIES EXPANSIONS

Figures 1-4 show the numerically derived time dependent altitude (y), velocity (v), acceleration (a), and jolt ($j=d^3y/dt^3$) from Eq. (4).¹⁴ They were created from a simple spreadsheet application of Euler's Method.¹⁵ Although these curves specifically represent Felix Baumgartner's jump of Table I, they are indicative of high altitude jumps in general. The altitude-time curve in Figure 1 ends at main parachute deployment. Figure 2 shows the velocity curve, its peak, and asymptotic approach to terminal velocity. Figures 3 and 4 show the acceleration and jolt curves with their respective extrema. From these figures, we can identify three regions primarily identified by peaks in functional solutions and two primarily defined by altitude air density characteristics. The five regions are listed in Table II.

Table II. Region and Range Definitions

Region	Range
1	$v = 0$ to peak velocity
2	$a = 0$ to peak positive acceleration
3	$j = 0$ to peak negative jolt
4	peak jolt to 10,000 m altitude
5	10,000 m to chute deployment

To begin the analysis, we write the generic Taylor series expansions for the altitude and, through differentiation, the velocity, acceleration, and jolt respectively for Eq. (4) as

$$y_i(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_{in} \Delta t^n, \quad (5)$$

$$v_i(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n c_{in} \Delta t^{n-1}, \quad (6)$$

$$a_i(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n(n-1) c_{in} \Delta t^{n-2}, \quad (10)$$

$$j_i(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} n(n-1)(n-2) c_{in} \Delta t^{n-3}. \quad (8)$$

In Eqs. (5)–(8), the factorial terms in the expansions have been included in the c_{in} coefficients. The subscript i refers to the region number, n refers to the expansion order number, and $\Delta t = t - t_{i0}$, where t_{i0} is the starting time at the beginning of each region, which is the ending time of the previous

region, which in turn represent the applicable peaks in Figures (2) – (4). The highest order number calculated for regions 1–3 is $n=5$. Region 4 contains an analytical solution based on a different approach than regions 1–3. Because the endpoints of one region will be the initial conditions for the next region, it is understood any errors in regional calculations will carry over into subsequent regions. Finally, the use of $1/\lambda_i$ in front of each sum is to compensate for a λ_i multiplied through each coefficient during derivations to allow grouping of similar terms in the final expressions. Defining a unique λ_i for each region allows the option of varying its value to account for atmospheric density rate changes.

Figure 1. Baumgartner's altitude vs time curve numerically calculated from Eq. (4) showing the five designated regions discussed in the text and shown individually in Figures 2-4.

Figure 2. Baumgartner's velocity vs time curve numerically calculated from Eq. (4) for region 1.

Figure 3. Baumgartner's acceleration vs time curve numerically calculated from Eq. (4) for region 2.

Figure 4. Baumgartner's jolt vs time curve numerically calculated from Eq. (4) highlighting regions 3, 4, and 5. Regions 4 and 5 are divided by altitude.

A. Region 1: Thin Air and Mach Speeds

In region 1, gravity dominates the early dynamics due to the very low air density, making the early velocity nearly linear in time. As the air density increases, drag increases until the two forces are equal and the acceleration is zero at peak velocity, as shown in Figures 2 and 3. Thus, region 1 is defined from $t=0$ to the peak velocity, v_{1p} , at time t_{1p} . Region 1 initial conditions are $t_{10}=0$, $y(0) = y_{10}$, $z(0) = z_{10}$, $v(0) = v_{10}=0$, $a(0) = a_{10} = -g$, and $j(0) = j_{10} = 0$. Given the initial conditions, the region 1 coefficients from Eq. (4) for Eqs. (5) – (8) are given in Table III.

Table III. Region 1 coefficients.

Coefficient	Expression
c_{10}	$\lambda_1 y_{10}/0!$
c_{11}	$\lambda_1 v_{10}/1! = 0$
c_{12}	$-\lambda_1(g - \lambda_1 z_{10} v_{10}^2/2)/2! = -\lambda_1 g/2!$
c_{14}	$(\lambda_1 g)^2 z_{10}/4!$
c_{16}	$(\lambda_1 g)^3 (6z_{10} - 4z_{10}^2)/6!$
c_{18}	$(\lambda_1 g)^4 (45z_{10} - 67z_{10}^2 + 10z_{10}^3)/8!$

In region 1, $c_{11} = 0$ since it represents the initial velocity, and all other odd coefficients are also zero. The coefficient c_{18} is not needed for region 1 calculations but is listed for illustrative purposes to show the increasing complexity in z_{10} with each order due to the nonlinearity of Eq. (4).

It should be noted that for very high altitudes and large terminal velocities, $z_{10} \ll 1$. The smaller z_{10} , the less orders are required for calculations in region 1.

Setting the acceleration expansion in Eq. (7) to zero and stopping at c_{i6} , results in an expansion in terms of Δt^2 giving the squared velocity peak time in Figure 2 as

$$\Delta t_{1p}^2 = \frac{-12c_{14} + \sqrt{144c_{14}^2 - 240c_{12}c_{16}}}{60c_{16}}, \quad (10)$$

or in terms of z_{10}

$$\Delta t_{1p}^2 = \frac{-6z_{10} + 12\sqrt{z_{10} - 5z_{10}^2/12}}{\lambda_1 g (6z_{10} - 4z_{10}^2)}. \quad (11)$$

To lowest order in z_{10} , which covers extreme jumps of interest, Eq. (11) simplifies to

$$\Delta t_{1p}^2(z_{10} \ll 1) \approx \frac{1}{\lambda_1 g} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{z_{10}}} - 1 \right). \quad (12)$$

The altitude at peak velocity and the peak velocity itself are found by substituting the peak time from Eqs. (10) or (11) into the expansions of Eqs. (5) and (6). However, substituting Eq. (12) instead, and retaining the lowest order in z_{10} gives the simplified expressions

$$y_{1p} \approx y_{10} - \frac{7}{15\lambda_1} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{z_{10}}} - 1 \right). \quad (13)$$

$$v_{1p} \approx -\frac{4}{5} \sqrt{\frac{g}{\lambda_1} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{z_{10}}} - 1 \right)}, \quad (14)$$

Substituting Eq. (14) into Eq. (13) provides the approximate relationship between peak velocity and the corresponding altitude as

$$y_{1p} \approx y_{10} - \frac{35}{48g} v_{1p}^2. \quad (15)$$

A direct relationship between y_{vp} , v_p , and v_t can be found by setting $dv/dt = 0$ in Eq. (4) giving

$$v_{1p} = v_t e^{\lambda_1 y_{1p}/2} \rightarrow y_{1p} = \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \ln\left(\frac{v_{1p}}{v_t}\right). \quad (16)$$

Equations (10) through (16) provide the solutions for time, altitude, and speed at peak velocity in region 1 solely on the initial conditions.

Example 1: Baumgartner

Although Baumgartner had a drogue chute available, he did not use it. Thus, his jump will serve as a true high-altitude freefall example. First, we need to choose values for λ_l and v_t . The parameter λ_l is the easier of the two to estimate by using the barometric formula which requires choosing a mean atmospheric temperature. Since temperature varies with altitude, the simplest approach is to choose a value of λ_l that gives reasonable values for air densities at altitudes of interest. For this study, values will be determined primarily by dividing the atmosphere into convenient blocks of $10,000\text{ m}$. For region 1, which occurs in the $30,000\text{ m}$ to $40,000\text{ m}$ range, $\lambda = 0.00014205/\text{m}$.

For Baumgartner's terminal velocity, the value of 50 m/s used in Ref. 10 will also be used here for all four regions, as well as $g = 9.8067\text{ m/s}^2$ for the acceleration of gravity.¹⁶

Table IV. Baumgartner's data versus calculations.

Jump Parameter	Reported	Calculated	Notes
Initial Altitude (m) $t_{10}=0, v_{10}=0$	38,969		$z_{10} \approx 0.21783$
Time (s) to Mach 1 or $\approx 310\text{ m/s}$	34	35	Root of Eq. (6) to c_{16}
Altitude (m) at Mach 1	33,446	33,767	Root of Eq. (5) to c_{16}
Time (s) to reach peak speed	50	51	Eq. (11)
Peak Speed (m/s)	377 Mach 1.25	373	Eq. (11) in Eq. (6) to c_{16}
Altitude (m) at peak speed	27,833	27,608	Eq. (11) in Eq. (5) to c_{16}

Example 2: Eustace

We now turn our attention to Eustace's jump where a drogue chute was used to stabilize his fall. If we apply the same Baumgartner parameter values to Eustace's jump, we find $z_{10} \approx 0.15306$, giving $v_p = 416\text{ m/s}$ from Eq. (14); a much higher value than reported in Table I. The use of a drogue chute, in general, would lower the value of the terminal velocity of 50 m/s used for Baumgartner's jump. Complicating the problem is the drogue chute wouldn't necessarily be fully deployed until reaching higher air densities, indicating a variable drag coefficient.¹² However, using Eq. (16) and Eustace's reported jump data, gives a terminal velocity of $\approx 42\text{ m/s}$ resulting in $z_{10} \approx 0.21693$. Although Eustace had a higher initial altitude than Baumgartner's, Eustace's lower

terminal velocity resulted in similar peak time and velocity to Baumgartner's, only shifted higher in altitude as shown in Table V.

Table V. Eustace data versus calculations.

Jump Parameter	Recorded	Calculated	Notes
Initial Jump Altitude (m) $t=0, v=0$	41,453	N/A	$z_0 \approx 0.21693$
Time (s) to reach peak speed	51	51	Eq. (11)
Peak Speed (m/s)	367 Mach 1.22	374	Eq. (11) in Eq. (6) to c_{16}
Altitude (m) at peak speed	30,500	30,064	Eq. (11) in Eq. (5) to c_{16}

Example 3: Kittinger

Kittinger's jump altitude was a record for a time but was much lower than the more recent jumps of Eustace and Baumgartner. Kittinger's jump was analyzed in Ref. 2, where a terminal velocity of ≈ 44 m/s was calculated from Kittinger's jump data. This would give Kittinger an initial value of $z_{10} \approx 0.91763$; a value too high to apply the equations derived here without adding higher orders or numerical solutions. However, the point of interest here is the terminal velocities of Kittinger and Eustace were calculated independently using different formulas yet are approximately the same. Assuming a roughly similar drag profile, since they both used drogue chutes but started from vastly different initial altitudes, the range of their terminal velocities of 42 m/s to 44 m/s may be taken as a first order estimate to use in high altitude jumps with drogue chutes.

Example 4: Minimum Altitude to reach Mach 1

A final region 1 calculation addresses the question of what is the lowest initial altitude that leads to a peak velocity of Mach 1 for a skydiver with zero initial velocity? Could Kittinger have reached Mach 1 if he didn't use a drogue chute? Since only a rough estimate is desired here, the simplest approach is to set the velocity of Eq. (14) to the speed of sound, v_s , and solve for the initial z_{s0} from the expression

$$z_{s0} = \left[\frac{32g}{(25\lambda_1 v_s^2 + 16g)} \right]^2. \quad (17)$$

The minimum initial altitude is then found from Eq. (3) as

$$y_{s0} = \frac{-1}{\lambda_1} \ln \frac{\lambda_1 z_{s0} v_t^2}{2g}. \quad (18)$$

The minor variation of sound with altitude and temperature is not important for the range of altitude differences here. Thus, we will use Baumgartner's value of 310 m/s, which gives $z_{s0} \approx 0.3968$ from Eq. (17). Although this value is not $\ll 1$, it will provide a fair result for the purposes of this discussion. From Eq. (18), this gives the minimum altitude at roughly $y_{s0} \approx 34,747$ m for a skydiver with $v_t \approx 50$ m/s and $y_{s0} \approx 36,547$ m for $v_t \approx 44$ m/s. Thus, even without a drogue chute, Kittinger could not have reached Mach 1 jumping at his altitude of 31,300 m.

B. Region 2: Peak Aerodynamic braking and Instabilities

Region 2 is defined between the points of peak velocity and peak positive acceleration, as shown in Figure 3. It is when the skydiver experiences the greatest aerodynamic braking. The region 2 expansion coefficients are given in Table VI, where $c_{22} = 0$ since it represents the acceleration at the beginning of region 2 as shown in Figure 3.

To find the time when the peak of the acceleration curve, t_{2p} occurs, we set the jolt of Eq. (8) equal to zero, and get

$$\Delta t_{2p} = \frac{-c_{24} - \sqrt{c_{24}^2 - 5c_{23}c_{25}/2}}{5c_{25}}, \quad (19)$$

where $\Delta t_{2p} = (t - t_{1p})$. Using Baumgartner as the case study, the values entered into the coefficients of Table VI are the outputs of Table IV. Thus, $y_{20} = y_{1p} \approx 27,608 \text{ m}$, $v_{20} = v_{1p} \approx -373 \text{ m/s}$, and $t_{20} = t_{1p} \approx 50.9 \text{ s}$. For the region 2 range of $20,000 \text{ m}$ to $30,000 \text{ m}$, $\lambda_2 \approx 0.00013697/\text{m}$.

Substituting the values above gives $\Delta t_{2p} \approx 14.4 \text{ s}$ after region 1, or approximately 65.3 after jumping. The altitude and velocity at this point, from Eqs. (5) and (6) are $\approx 22,510 \text{ m}$ and $\approx -321 \text{ m/s}$ respectively. Equation (7) gives a peak positive acceleration of 5.76 m/s^2 . For Baumgartner, we find the altitude difference between the peak velocity and peak positive acceleration was approximately $5,098 \text{ m}$. These numbers coincide very well with the time, speed, and altitude when Baumgartner reported uncontrolled, potentially fatal, spins and other instabilities, and as recorded during the jump. The time duration of the spin was reported as approximately 13 s , coinciding with the time to peak acceleration calculated above.^{7,8}

Table VI. Region 2 coefficients.

Coefficient	Expression
c_{20}	$\lambda_2 y_{1p}/0!$
c_{21}	$\lambda_2 v_{1p}/1!$
c_{22}	$-\lambda_2(g - \lambda_2 z_{1p} v_{1p}^2/2)/2! = 0$
c_{23}	$-(\lambda_2 v_{1p})^3 z_{1p}/(2 \cdot 3!)$
c_{24}	$(\lambda_2 v_{1p})^4 (z_{1p} - z_{1p}^2)/(2 \cdot 4!)$
c_{25}	$(\lambda_2 v_{1p})^5 (7z_{1p}^2 - 2z_{1p}^3)/(4 \cdot 5!)$

The instabilities experienced by Baumgartner were mostly avoided by Eustace with his use of a drogue chute. If we apply the same region 2 analysis to Eustace's jump, we find he reached a peak positive acceleration nearly the same as Baumgartner at 5.78 m/s^2 , at a speed of 322 m/s , but at an altitude $\approx 2,515 \text{ m}$ higher. A seemingly small relative difference in height, but the air density at Eustace's peak acceleration was approximately 70% of Baumgartner's at his peak acceleration.

C. Region 3: Return to Stability

Following the derivations in the previous sections, the expansion coefficients for region 3 are given in Table VII. The coefficient $c_{33} = 0$ because the initial jolt in region 3 is zero, as shown in Figure 4. For Baumgartner, the inputs to region 3 are: $y_{30} = y_{2p} \approx 22,510 \text{ m}$, $v_{30} = v_{2p} \approx -321 \text{ m/s}$,

$t_{30} = t_{1p} \approx 65.3$ s. For Baumgartner, region 3 straddles the 20,000 m altitude, thus we will set $\lambda_3 \approx 0.00012417/m$; which represents the 10,000 m to 20,000 m block. The time to peak jolt is given by taking the derivative of Eq. (8) and setting it equal to zero giving¹⁷

$$\Delta t_{3p} = -\frac{c_{34}}{5c_{35}}. \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) gives $\Delta t_{3p} \approx 3.6$ s. From Eqs. (5) – (6), at the jolt peak, $y_{3p} \approx 21,464$ m and $v_{3p} \approx -268$ m/s. The total times of regions 2 and 3 coincide well with Baumgartner’s observation of the time he regained stability and with recorded data.⁸

Table VII. Region 3 coefficients.

Coefficient	Expression
c_{30}	$\lambda_3 y_{2p}/0!$
c_{31}	$\lambda_3 v_{2p}/1!$
c_{32}	$-\lambda_3(g - \lambda_3 z_{2p} v_{2p}^2/2)/2!$
c_{33}	$-\lambda_3^2[2gz_{2p}v_{2p} + \lambda_3(z_{2p} - z_{2p}^2)v_{2p}^3]/(2 \cdot 3!) = 0$
c_{34}	$\lambda_3^2[\alpha_{34} + \beta_{34} + \gamma_{34}]/(2 \cdot 4!)$ $\alpha_{34} = 2g^2 z_{2p}, \beta_{34} = \lambda_3 g(5z_{2p} - 2z_{2p}^2)v_{2p}^2,$ $\gamma_{34} = \lambda_3^2(2z_{2p} - 5z_{2p}^2 + z_{2p}^3)v_{2p}^4/2$
c_{35}	$\lambda_3^2[\alpha_{35} + \beta_{35} + \gamma_{35}]/(2 \cdot 5!)$ $\alpha_{35} = -2\lambda_3 g^2(6z_{2p} - z_{2p}^2)v_{2p}$ $\beta_{35} = -\lambda_3^2 g(9z_{2p} - 17z_{2p}^2 + 2z_{2p}^3)v_{2p}^3$ $\gamma_{35} = -\lambda_3^3(2z_{2p} - 11z_{2p}^2 + 11z_{2p}^3 - z_{2p}^4)v_{2p}^5/2$

D. Regions 4 and 5: Entering the Troposphere and Main Chute Deployment

Reference 10 discusses a solution for Eq. (4) for velocity as a function of altitude given by

$$v[z(y)] = \left\{ \frac{2g}{\lambda} e^{-z} [Ei(z) + C_1] \right\}^{1/2}, \quad (21)$$

where $Ei(z)$ is the exponential integral and C_1 is the constant of integration.¹⁸ For the typical high-altitude skydiver with $v_0 = 0$, $C_1 = -Ei(z_0)$, and for small z can be calculated from

$$Ei(z) = \int_{-\infty}^z \frac{\exp(x)}{x} dx = \gamma + \ln(z) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{kk!}. \quad (22)$$

The symbol γ ($= 0.5772\dots$) is the Euler-Mascheroni_constant. The series in Eq. (22) could have been used above for region 1 where $z \ll 1$. However, the appearance of the $\ln(z)$ makes its use awkward for finding roots and other quantities of interest. Furthermore, the solution gives $v(y)$, whereas the desired solution relates v and t . The series approach used in regions 1-3 bypassed this difficulty by directly expanding Eq. (4) in time.

When the skydiver enters region 4, near the 20,000 m altitude, and transitions into the troposphere, which contains approximately 80% of the earth’s atmosphere, z has become large enough to take advantage of a large argument solution to Eq. (21). The goal is to find a solution

that relates time with the velocity and altitude, in order to calculate the remaining quantity of interest; the total freefall time.

For large z values, the exponential integral has the expansion

$$Ei(z \gg 1) \approx \frac{e^z}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{k!}{z^k} = \frac{e^z}{z} \left(1 + \frac{1}{z} + \frac{2}{z^2} + \frac{6}{z^3} \dots \right). \quad (23)$$

To acquire a simple analytical solution from Eq. (21) using Eq. (23), we first note the value z at the end of region 3 is large enough to truncate Eq. (23) to second order. This approximation improves rapidly within a few seconds after entering region 4, and at $y = 2,000 \text{ m}$, $z \gtrsim 50$ for a typical skydiver. Therefore, the velocity from Eq. (21), to second order using Eq. (23), is given by

$$v = - \left[\frac{2g}{\lambda} \left(\frac{z+1}{z^2} + C_1 e^{-z} \right) \right]^{1/2}, \quad (24)$$

where C_1 is now defined by

$$C_1 = \left[\frac{\lambda}{2g} v_{40}^2 - \frac{z_{40} + 1}{z_{40}^2} \right] e^{z_{40}}. \quad (25)$$

We now need a relationship between v , z , and t that allows finding $v(t)$. That relationship is found from the time derivative of Eq. (2), giving $dz/dt = -\lambda z v$, which, using Eq. (24), results in

$$\int \frac{dz}{\sqrt{[(z+1)(1 + \frac{C_1 z^2 e^{-z}}{z+1})]}} = \sqrt{2\lambda g} t + C_2, \quad (26)$$

where C_2 is a constant of integration.

The integral in Eq. (26) cannot be evaluated in terms of elementary functions unless further simplified. Since the initial value of z is large in region 4, for the problem of interest here, the term containing C_1 in Eq. (26) is typically < 1 , and rapidly decreases to $\ll 1$. Thus, the expression can be binomially expanded.¹⁹ Keeping the first order term results in the equation

$$\int \frac{dz}{\sqrt{z+1}} - \frac{C_1}{2} \int \frac{z^2 e^{-z}}{(z+1)^{3/2}} dz = \sqrt{2\lambda g} t + C_2. \quad (27)$$

The integral with the C_1 coefficient has the solution

$$\left[-\frac{7e\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{z+1}) - \frac{(z+3)}{\sqrt{z+1}} e^{-z} \right]_{z_{40}}^z, \quad (28)$$

where erf refers to the error function. Due to large z values, the difference in the erf functions at z_{40} and z is negligible, thus the erf term can be dropped in Eq. (28) leaving only the second term. The time from Eq. (26) is now given by

$$t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda g}} \left[2\sqrt{z+1} + \frac{C_1}{2} \frac{(z+3)e^{-z}}{\sqrt{z+1}} - C_2 \right], \quad (29)$$

where all the constant terms have been absorbed into C_2 such that $t=0$ at $z = z_{40}$.

Since Eq. (29) gives t as a function z , it also connects to both y and v through Eqs. (2) and (24) respectively. The output for region 3, given in the last section, becomes the input to Eq. (29). The

splitting of the last 20,000 m to regions 4 and 5 is necessary due to the large differences in λ for the respective regions. For region 4, 20,000 m to 10,000 m, and region 5, 10,000 m to ground, the values are, $\lambda_4 = 0.00012417/m$ and $\lambda_5 = 0.00010563/m$. Finally, the output of region 4 becomes the input to region 5.

The important parameter to calculate is the final total free fall time, since this is a key data point for record contention and influences at which altitude or speed chute deployment is initiated. This can be calculated through Eq. (29) as a region 5 event. Baumgartner's z value entering region 5 is ≈ 26 and the reported chute deployment occurred at $y \approx 2,567$ m or $z \approx 56$. Substituting $z \approx 56$ into Eq. (29) gives $t \approx 106$ s after entering region 5. The total freefall time, t_f , is the sum of all the regional times, which for Baumgartner is $\approx 51+14+4+78+106 = 253$ seconds. The official reported time is 260 seconds.⁷ The discrepancy is largely due to the slightly higher calculated speed in the later phase of region 5 compared to actual recorded speeds. At chute deployment, Baumgartner's speed was reported at ≈ 51 m/s compared to the calculated value of ≈ 57 m/s. Part of this could also be attributed to terminal velocity being velocity dependent, as opposed to a constant value assumed here.^{6,12}

A good region 5 approximation can be made by making use of the z value at very low altitudes. At these low altitudes, the C_1 term in Eq. (29) can be dropped and the $z+1$ term can be retained or simply replaced by z . Dropping the 1 in $z+1$ leads to the following approximate $y(t)$ and $v(t)$ region 5 equations for large z

$$y \approx -\frac{2}{\lambda_5} \ln[\sqrt{\beta} (\alpha t + C_2/2)], \quad (30)$$

$$v \approx -\frac{2\alpha/\lambda_5}{(\alpha t + C_2/2)}, \quad (31)$$

where

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\lambda_5 g/2} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \sqrt{\lambda_5 v_t^2/2g}. \quad (32)$$

At $y=0$, the \ln argument in Eq. (30) must equal 1, and when substituted into the denominator of Eq. (31) gives $v(y=0) = v_t$. Figure 5 shows the five combined regional velocity solutions compared to a simple numerical Euler's Method solution and with Baumgartner's raw data.^{8,9} The gray area centered on region 3 designates when Baumgartner experienced instabilities and coincides with his peak positive acceleration.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Five regional Taylor series solutions were developed for the problem of the extreme high-altitude skydiver. Besides altitude and velocity as functions of time, higher derivatives were calculated. It was shown that, for the case of Felix Baumgartner who did not use a drogue chute, severe instabilities experienced during his jump coincided with his peak positive acceleration acting as a braking mechanism as he reached higher air densities. Calculated altitude and velocities as function of time were in good agreement with recorded data, as well as the total freefall time.

The analysis presented here offers new insights into the understanding of the extreme skydiver problem which can be beneficial from student to professional levels. Furthermore, the problem allows students to examine how a typical physics model increases in complexity as more conditions are applied. In this case, from free fall with zero drag, to free fall with constant drag, to free fall with variable drag, and whatever conditions students may wish to add, for example, gravity as a function of altitude.

Figure 5. The five combined regional velocity solutions (dash line) compared to a numerical Euler's Method solution (dotted line) and with Baumgartner's raw data (solid line). The vertical dotted bars delineate the five regions. The shaded area highlights the region of instabilities.

REFERENCES

1. D. Kindy, "The Man who Fell to Earth," National Air and Space Museum, (July 2023), see <https://airandspace.si.edu/air-and-space-quarterly/summer-2023/space-jumper>.
2. P. Mohazzabi and J.H. Shea, "High-altitude freefall," *Am. J. Phys.* 64, 1242-1246 (1996).
3. Stratopedia, see Andreev, E.N. (1926-2000), <https://stratocat.com.ar/stratopedia/124.htm>.
4. M. Majendie, "Felix Baumgartner on Red Bull Stratos: the day the black sky turned blue," (October 2022), see <https://www.redbull.com/us-en/felix-baumgartner-stratos-10-years>.
5. A. Müller, "Supersonic Jump," *Phys. Teach.* 51(1), 14, (January 2013).
6. Gossling A., Becker S., and Kuhn J., "Hands on Experiment for Modeling the Baumgartner Jump Using Free-Fall Kinematics with Drag," *Phys. Teach.* 59, 111-113 (2021).
7. See <https://www.redbull.com/int-en/red-bull-stratos-release-mission-data>.
8. See <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0187798>.
9. See <https://www.scienceworld.ca/resource/stratos-jump-data-analysis/>.
10. T. Corvo, "An analytical solution to the extreme skydiver problem," *Phys. Teach.* 57, 289 (2019).
11. World Air Sports Federation, "Yet to be beaten: Alan Eustace's high-altitude parachute jump records still stand, 10 years on," (October 2024), see <https://www.fai.org/news/alan-eustace-high-altitude-parachute-jump-records-tenth-anniversary>.
12. J. Leidich and J. Straus, "Analyzing a Drogue-Stabilized Human Freefall from the Stratosphere," 23rd AIAA Aerodynamic Decelerator Systems Technology Conference, 30 Mar – 2 Apr, Daytona Beach, FL.
13. F. Sears and G. Salinger, (1975), *Thermodynamics, Kinetic Theory, and Statistical Thermodynamics*, Third Edition, Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, Philippines

14. Sometimes also referred to as “jerk.”
15. See <https://www.uah.edu/images/people/faculty/howellkb/DEText-Ch9.pdf>.
16. Input parameters will be defined up to five significant figures; however, all calculated results are minimally given to the number of significant figures used in reported values.
17. The solution for peak time in region 3 is linear compared to regions 1 and 2 due to the complexity of calculating higher order coefficients in these midrange altitudes as can be seen in Table VII for c_{34} and c_{35} . Therefore, Eq. (8) for region 3 is quadratic in time containing only coefficients c_{34} and c_{35} , resulting in a linear solution after differentiation.
18. Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables, Milton Abramowitz and Irene A. Stegun editors, U.S. Department of Commerce, National Bureau of Standards, pp. 227-251, (June 1964).
19. In the cases where this term is not < 1 at the bringing of the region, Eq. (27) returns a negative time until z is large enough to make the approximation correct. Typically, this is only for a few seconds since z increases rapidly.